

Landscape Scale Definition Based on Maximum Spatial Heterogeneity: a Methodological Proposal

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Abstract

Remote sensing offers opportunities to analyse landscape heterogeneity across multiple spatial scales, which is critical for understanding ecological processes and land use dynamics. This study presents a methodological workflow designed to identify the landscape scale that maximises spatial heterogeneity, measured using the normalized Shannon Diversity Index, from categorical land use and land cover maps. The workflow iteratively samples random landscape scales of increasing size within a study region, calculates the index for each, and summarises the results through distributions of median values to reveal scale-dependent patterns of heterogeneity. The method was applied to a case study in Mojuí dos Campos, a municipality in the Brazilian Amazon, using TerraClass 2022 data. Results show that SHDI increases with landscape size, peaking at 6,000 m before stabilizing, indicating an optimal spatial extent for landscape analysis that balances compositional richness and configurational evenness. While promising, the approach could benefit from enhancements such as proportional sampling, incorporation of alternative diversity metrics, and implementation in a programmable environment for automation and scalability. Future work will also apply rigorous statistical tests, including the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, to validate scale selection. This workflow provides a reproducible and transferable framework to guide ecologically relevant landscape-scale assessments in heterogeneous and human-modified environments.

1 Introduction

Remote sensing has revolutionised the observation and analysis of ecological patterns, providing large-scale and high-frequency data suitable for landscape studies. Landscape ecology is a multidisciplinary field that investigates the relationship between spatial patterns and ecological processes across multiple spatial and temporal scales [7, 13]. A landscape is commonly defined as an area that is spatially heterogeneous in at least one relevant attribute. At the human scale, it can be described as a mosaic of distinct ecosystems and habitat types [4].

Landscape heterogeneity, the variation in the composition and configuration of spatial elements over space and time, is one of the key features driving ecological dynamics. Importantly, spatial heterogeneity is dependent on the scale's spatial extent at which it is measured [5, 9]. Selecting an appropriate spatial resolution of analysis is therefore crucial, as it influences the spatial patterns observed and the ecological interpretations derived from them [7].

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The concept of scale encompasses two fundamental dimensions: grain, which refers to the smallest unit of observation (e.g., a pixel in a satellite image), and extent, which defines the overall area of analysis (e.g., a subsection of an image). Both dimensions affect the heterogeneity captured and the inferences that follow [13]. Thus, defining an optimal spatial extent based on measurable heterogeneity can enhance the ecological relevance and consistency of landscape analyses.

In many tropical regions, heterogeneity is intensified by land use and land cover change, particularly through mosaic and smallholder agricultural systems that produce fine-scale patchiness by combining croplands, pastures, fallows, secondary forests, and remnant vegetation [12]. From a remote sensing perspective, such landscapes present increased classification complexity and information richness due to their structural variability and land cover diversity [3]. As a result, human-modified landscapes can exhibit high compositional and configurational heterogeneity, making the identification of scale thresholds essential for understanding fragmentation dynamics and spatial integrity in diverse environments [10].

In this context, this study proposes a methodological workflow to identify the landscape extent that maximises spatial heterogeneity in categorical thematic maps derived from remote sensing. The approach is based on the computation of the Shannon Diversity Index (SHDI), a widely used metric for quantifying landscape heterogeneity in terms of classes' richness and evenness [8], across a range of spatial extents. By integrating multiscale extent analysis with this metric, the workflow provides a conceptual and analytical foundation for defining ecologically relevant spatial units across heterogeneous environments.

2 Methodology

2.1 Methodological workflow

The methodological workflow (Figure 1) developed in this study is designed to be later adapted into a programmable structure, allowing specific parameters to be defined. The input consists of a raster dataset of a region of interest, where each pixel represents a land use and land cover class (i.e., categorical data). An initial landscape extent, a final landscape extent, and a step value, by which landscape extents will be incrementally analysed, must be defined. In this workflow, landscapes are represented as square cells of increasing size.

Figure 1. Methodological workflow.

The process begins by randomly selecting m coordinate points within the study area. From each point, a square landscape of the initial landscape extent is drawn. For each of these m landscapes, the corresponding portion of the raster map is extracted, and the normalized Shannon Diversity Index (SHDI) is calculated according to Equation 1. This index was selected to quantify spatial heterogeneity because it accounts for both the richness of land cover classes and the evenness of their distribution within each landscape [8].

$$\text{SHDI} = \frac{-\sum_{i=1}^k p_i \cdot \ln(p_i)}{\ln(k)} \quad (1)$$

In SHDI, p_i represents the pixel proportion of category i in the landscape, computed as $p_i = \frac{n_i}{N}$, where n_i is the number of pixels belonging to category i , and N is the total number of valid pixels in the landscape. The summation runs over all k possible categories in the classification. The denominator $\ln(k)$ corresponds to the maximum possible entropy when all k categories are equally represented. This normalization bounds SHDI in the interval $[0, 1]$, where 0 indicates complete dominance (a single category) and 1 represents maximum diversity with equal proportions across all categories.

The median of the m SDHI values is computed and stored. The median is preferred over the mean in this context as it reduces the influence of outliers, providing a more robust central tendency measure for skewed SHDI distributions. This entire procedure is repeated over n iterations to account for variability in the sampling process. For each landscape extent, the resulting values are summarised as a boxplot showing the distribution of median values across iterations. The same procedure is repeated for each new landscape extent, by incrementing the initial extent using the defined step until the final extent is reached. Finally, a sequence of boxplots is generated, displaying the distribution of SHDI medians for each landscape extent. This visualisation enables the identification of the spatial extent at which heterogeneity, as measured by the SHDI, reaches its maximum.

2.2 Case study

As a case study, the proposed methodological workflow was applied to the municipality of Mojuí dos Campos, located in the western portion of the state of Pará, in the Brazilian Amazon (Figure 2). This region has experienced significant land use transformation since the late 1990s, primarily driven by the expansion of soybean cultivation. The process intensified in 2003 following the construction of Cargill's export port in the nearby city of Santarém. Since then, Mojuí dos Campos has undergone notable land use and land cover (LULC) changes, with many forested areas and smallholder agricultural plots being converted to mechanised soybean plantations [1]. These characteristics make the region especially suitable for testing the proposed method for identifying a suitable spatial extent of analysis based on maximum heterogeneity.

Figure 2. Study area.

The data used in this study are from the TerraClass system for the year 2022, and the study area includes ten (10) land use and land cover (LULC) classes. The initial landscape extent was set to 1×1 km, the final extent to 10×10 km, and the step increment to 1 km. A total of 100 random points were sampled, and the procedure was repeated over 100 iterations to ensure statistical robustness. As a result, the analysis gener-

ates a graph with ten boxplots, each representing the distribution of median SHDI values corresponding to each landscape extent.

3 Results and Discussion

Figure 3 presents the distribution of median SHDI values across the range of tested landscape extents for the study area. The results show that median SHDI values are relatively low (< 0.3) at the smallest extent (1,000 m) but steadily increase with larger landscape extents, reaching a peak around 6,000 m. Beyond this threshold, values appear to stabilize, with no substantial gains in heterogeneity observed up to the maximum tested extent of 10,000 m. According to the criteria adopted in this study, a landscape extent of approximately 6,000 m represents the optimal scale for capturing maximum spatial heterogeneity in the region, and would therefore be recommended for landscape-scale analyses of land use and land cover (LULC) patterns.

Figure 3. Distribution of SHDI over different landscape extents.

There is no universal optimal scale for landscape analysis, it depends on the study context and objectives. Nevertheless, empirical and theoretical studies support using peaks in landscape heterogeneity as meaningful indicators for scale selection [2, 6]. For example, [14] demonstrated that diversity-related landscape metrics often exhibit clear inflection points at specific extents, marking scales at which structure is most informative. Likewise, [11] emphasize that multiscale approaches can reveal the ecological processes most clearly when analyzed at these scales. It is also important to note that SHDI captures diversity by incorporating both richness (composition) and evenness (configuration) of landscape classes. In our study, the stabilization of SHDI beyond 6,000 m indicates a convergence in composition and configuration, suggesting that this extent captures the main spatial heterogeneity without redundant detail.

Despite the promising results, this study has some limitations. First, although the SHDI metric captures both composition and configuration aspects of landscape heterogeneity, it represents only one dimension of landscape structure; additional metrics addressing connectivity or fragmentation could provide complementary insights. Second, the landscape extents analyzed were tested at discrete intervals, which may limit the precision in identifying the true optimal scale of maximum heterogeneity. Third, the approach was tested in a single municipality within the Brazilian Amazon, and the optimal scale identified here may not directly apply to regions with different land use histories, patch structures, or levels of fragmentation. Finally, the methodology has yet to be implemented in a programmable and automated environment, which may constrain reproducibility and scalability across broader spatial or temporal extents.

4 Conclusion

This study proposed a methodological workflow to assist in defining an optimal landscape scale based on maximum heterogeneity of landscape classes. The approach was demonstrated using a case study from an Amazonian municipality, producing a series of boxplots that display the distribution of median SHDI values across different landscape extents. Certain steps could be refined, for example, by distributing random sampling points proportionally to the extent of each landscape unit or by incorporating alternative diversity metrics such as the Simpson Index. To improve robustness and reproducibility, future work will focus on developing a toolbox that implements this methodology in a programmable language, allowing for automated and scalable analyses. Additionally, statistical rigor will be enhanced by systematically comparing pairwise median SHDI distributions across scales using the two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test to validate scale selection more rigorously. Together, these improvements aim to create a more objective and transferable tool for landscape scale selection.

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